

Let's care

BUILDING SAFE AND CARING SCHOOLS
TO FOSTER EDUCATIONAL INCLUSION
AND SCHOOL ACHIEVEMENT

D 6.2 Plan for Dissemination and Exploitation including Communication Activities

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. Executive Summary	7
PART A – INTRODUCTION TO THE PLAN FOR DISSEMINATION AND EXPLOITATION.....	8
1. Introduction.....	8
2. Internal communication process.....	9
3. Dissemination and Exploitation general plan.....	10
Part B - COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION PLANS.....	12
1. Purpose of Communication and Dissemination	12
2. Tailoring the communication and dissemination activities on the project.....	13
3. Co-creation process in the framework of Communication and Dissemination	15
4. Target groups.....	16
5. Categories of messages	17
5.1 Main messages to be shared	20
.....	22
.....	23
Communication plan	25
1. Outreach activities.....	25
2. Communication materials	26
2.1. Digital newsletter	26
2.2. Promotional videos.....	26
2.3. Supporting communication material.....	27
2.4. Press releases and interviews.....	27
3. Communication channels	27
3.1. LET'S CARE website.....	28
3.2. LET'S CARE Hub.....	29
3.3. Social Media	30
3.4. Newsletters and mailing.....	32
Dissemination plan	32
1. Multiplier events organised by the consortium	33
2. Participation to events and Networking.....	34

- 3. Clustering with other EU platforms, networks and initiatives37
- 4. Policy and advocacy actions38
- 5. Activities addressed to the scientific community.....39
 - 5.1. Participation to scientific conferences and seminars.....39
 - 5.2. Scientific publications39
- Communication and dissemination monitoring.....44
 - 1. Work-plan of the communication and dissemination plan44
 - 2. Reporting and KPI44
 - 3.46
 - 5. Communication and dissemination data collection46
- Part C - EXPLOITATION STRATEGY AND IPR.....53
 - 1. Introduction.....53
 - 2. The exploitation social dimension.....53
 - 3. Exploitation Strategy and IPR management.....54
 - 4. Schedule of Exploitation Strategy55
 - 4.1. Stage 1. Definition of IP Management Plan56
 - 4.2. Stage 2. Identification of Key Results57
 - 4.3. Stage 3. Evaluation of Key Ideas58
 - 4.4. Stage 4. Exploitation strategy generation59
 - 4.5. Stage 5. Updated IP Management Plan.....62
 -62
 - 4.6. Stage 6. Networking with Projects & Initiatives63
 - 5. IPR Management Strategy63
 - 6. Mapping of existing patents and potentially IPR overlapping for the future Foreground.....64
 - 7. Assessment of the knowledge generated in the project (Foreground)64
 - 8. First definition of IP results' protection possibilities.....65
- Annex 1 – Internal communication: processes, structure and tools.....68
- Annex 2 - External Communication and Dissemination potential of the consortium71
- Annex 3 – Type of information shared with each target group73
- Annex 4 – LET’S CARE website.....76
- Annex 5 – LET’S CARE hub77

Annex 6 – Examples of dissemination events the partners will organize and participate to78

Annex 7 – Initial plan for the participation to conferences and events addressed to the education scientific community.....80

Annex 8 – Communication and dissemination Gantt.....84

Annex 9 - Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for Communication and Dissemination85

Annex 10 – Communication and dissemination reporting table87

Annex 11 - Exploitation canvas explanatory overview.....91

Annex 12 - Recommendations made by the IPR Helpdesk regarding results that are not protected94

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Description
CoS	Community of Schools
SEG	School Education Gateway
HEU	Horizon Europe (funding programme)
SEO	Search Engine Optimization
PMAB	Policy Makers Advisory Board
EEN	European Education Policy Network
EESC	European Economic and Social Committee
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
IP	Intellectual Property
WP	Work Package
CA	Consortium Agreement
GA	Grant Agreement
EB	Executive Board
PAR	Participatory Action Research
TG	Target Groups

1. Executive Summary

The present document outlines LET'S CARE Dissemination and Exploitation plans and provides strategies of the project partners with guidelines to generate a deep impact of the project's results by attracting the interest of the main stakeholders and target groups.

In order to maximize the overall impact of the project, create awareness among target audiences and facilitate the adoption of innovative outputs developed within the project framework, the Plan carefully integrates three core elements: communication, dissemination and exploitation. These elements are detailed in specific sections, while the main framework of the plan is described in the introduction. Thus, the document is divided into three main parts, providing:

A) Introduction to the main concepts of the Dissemination and Exploitation Plan: definitions, connection between dissemination and exploitation and phases of the plan.

B) Relevant guidance on the preparation, development, evaluation and reporting of the **communication and dissemination activities**. This part is composed by two sections:

- Communication plan: identifies actions and communication tools to ensure that information about the project reaches all the interested stakeholders.
- Dissemination plan: includes the description of actions that has to be implemented in order to ensure the proper diffusion of project's main results and outputs, the active engagement of the target groups and the concrete involvement of stakeholders in project's activities.

C) Plan for the Intellectual Property management and the **exploitation activities** that have to be carried out during and after the project to ensure that all results are properly valorised as replicable future products and services. This part details all the seven phases of the exploitation process.

PART A – INTRODUCTION TO THE PLAN FOR DISSEMINATION AND EXPLOITATION

1. Introduction

LET'S CARE project aims to comprehensively research and assess the value of the caring dimension of educational inclusion and academic success. Hence, LET'S CARE will create a theoretical and practical framework to foster Safe Learning, Safe Teaching, Safe Schools, and Safe Education at each educational level, as an innovative approach to interrupt the recurrence of educational and social exclusion generation by generation. This framework will contribute to tackling school failure, poor academic results and early school leaving.

LET'S CARE will develop and test some innovative approaches both in conceptual and methodological dimensions, starting from deep desk research to move towards the fieldwork. The project aims to collect and systematize good practices related to school guidance for teachers, school communities and the policy level. The Safe Education model will be tested in at least six European countries. Evidence-based policy recommendations will be developed by involving relevant stakeholders at the local, national, and international levels in a co-creation and collaboration mechanism.

The implementation of the project and the successful promotion of its results, require a solid and clear strategy of Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation. All these three aspects are strictly interconnected, and they are all essential to achieve a successful outcome maximizing LET'S CARE impact and reach.

- **Communication: Inform, promote and communicate activities and results**

Communication refers to the process of promoting project's aims, activities, and results to reach citizen, media and stakeholders through different channels. The main aims of communication are to engage with stakeholders, attract experts, raise awareness (also of how public money is spent), show the success of European collaboration. Its activities run from the start of the action until the end.

- **Dissemination: Make knowledge and results a common good to make the research step forward**

Dissemination refers to the process of sharing and spreading the knowledge gained throughout the project with the relevant stakeholders in order to maximise results' impact, allow other researchers to go a step forward, contribute to the advancement of the state of the art, make scientific results a common good. Dissemination addresses those who can learn and benefit from the results, such as: teachers, school directors, scientists, public authorities, policymakers, civil society. Its activities run at any time, and as soon as the action has results.

- **Exploitation: to make concrete use of the results for societal and political purposes**

Exploitation refers to the process of using information, knowledge, and ideas to achieve specific purposes (societal, political) by addressing those that can take the project results forward: researchers, authorities, policymakers, sectors of interest, civil society. It is essential to ensure that the benefits of the project are realized and can be sustained over the long term. The main aims of exploitation is to lead to innovative legislation or recommendations and help to tackle the problem of early school leaving and underachievement. Its main activities start towards the end and beyond as soon as the project has exploitable results.

2. Internal communication process

To tackle the challenges of coordinating efforts across various institutions and countries, it is necessary to setting up a comprehensive internal communication strategy that promotes open dialogue, supports the exchange of ideas, and ensures smooth cooperation among the partners. The approach to the internal communication is tailored to meet the specific needs and inputs of each participant, guaranteeing that every member's perspective is respected and considered. A well-organized yet adaptable communication framework, will facilitate efficient information exchange, enabling the consortium to proactively tackle obstacles and share fruitfully the knowledge.

LET'S CARE internal communication plan will utilize a combination of synchronous (in presence and virtual meetings) and asynchronous (emails and digital workspace) tools to facilitate the collaboration. This comprehensive approach ensures that all partners stay connected and well-informed, overcoming any challenges posed by geographical distances and varying time zones. The main tools and platforms that will be used to facilitate the collaboration are as follows:

- Real-Time online communication: video conferencing tool (Huddle.team platform from FreeConferenceCall) for meetings, workshops, and brainstorming sessions.
- Asynchronous communication: emails for communications and updates.
- Shared digital workspace: cloud storage solution for accessible document storage and collaboration (Nextcloud).

Each WP leader will be responsible to adapt the following guidelines to the needs of the partners and to the internal work plan of the WP.

The detailed description of the internal communication process, tools and structure is reported in Annex 1.

3. Dissemination and Exploitation general plan

The Dissemination and Exploitation Plan is a strategic blueprint designed to ensure the efficient and effective sharing and utilization of the project's results, research outputs and good practices. By carefully integrating the three core elements - communication, dissemination, and exploitation - the Plan aims to maximize the overall impact of the project, create awareness among target audiences and facilitate the adoption of innovative solutions developed within the project framework.

The exploitation and dissemination of a project's results are closely interconnected, as they both aim to maximize the impact and reach of the project outcomes. A well-planned and executed dissemination strategy can significantly enhance the potential for successful exploitation, while effective exploitation can further amplify the project's impact and reach. By integrating these two aspects from the project planning stage, LET'S CARE can maximise the value and impact of its research and innovation efforts.

Communication, dissemination and exploitation activities will take place throughout the duration of the project. We can identify three main stages of implementation of the Plan that reflect the strategy to maximise the project's visibility, incidence and impact:

- 1. SEED stage (M1-M12)** focuses on creating a foundation for communication, dissemination, and exploitation. It involves identifying main channels, resources, messages, and target groups to ensure the project's visibility and recognition. This phase is pivotal for developing a comprehensive framework tailored to meet the project's goals effectively. Key objectives include clarifying partner responsibilities and establishing a strategic direction for internal and external information sharing, with a strong emphasis on communication activities phase.
- 2. FLOURISHING stage (M13-M42)** capitalizes on established communication pathways to disseminate project results and promote best practices. It targets the effective sharing of research outputs with key groups, stakeholder engagement, and enhanced consortium collaboration. This phase is crucial for ensuring the project's outputs are primed for adoption by the intended audience, aiming to maximize the project's broader impact. Here, the focus shifts more towards dissemination efforts to secure long-term project success.
- 3. HARVESTING stage (M43-72)** builds upon previous phases and strategies how to better exploit the results of the project even after its ending. This phase will be oriented to define the commitments of the consortium beyond the project life-time to maximize the overall impact of the project's results, including the LET'S CARE tools and networks. This is the phase in which the long-term sustainability of the project is set up and the potential impact of the project is maximized by establishing the processes and plans for its exploitation. Exploitation activities predominate in this phase.

The consortium has the potential to successfully promote the project and to disseminate its results among broad target groups. The KPIs defined in the project proposal and confirmed in this plan are supported by the analysis of the partners' potential impact. Tables with specific data can be found in Annex 2.

Part B - COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION PLANS

Communication and dissemination activities will be implemented since the beginning of the project in order to facilitate the project's outputs and results to reach all the target groups and key stakeholders. However, communication and dissemination are not just elements or outputs of a project, they are strategic tools, closely interconnected with all other project elements and dimensions, contributing to achieving the project's goals especially those connected with the aims of influencing society and reverting exclusion dynamics.

The communication and dissemination plan support this process providing the consortium with the main guidelines to:

- a) Identify the target audiences and stakeholders and define concrete communication actions toward each group.
- b) Implement an innovative and multiplier-effect communication campaign.
- c) Set up the different communication channels and tools tailored to target audiences.
- d) Monitor the impact of the communication and dissemination activities in order to apply corrective actions whenever necessary and identify opportunities that can maximise the impact and visibility of the project.

1. Purpose of Communication and Dissemination

The main scope of LET'S CARE Communication and Dissemination plans is to build up and foster participation and engagement of stakeholders and target groups throughout the project's duration. Communication and Dissemination are aimed to:

- a) Incorporate stakeholders' point of view in the co-created approach to the project.
- b) Promote social awareness about the importance of a Safe Learning for all learners, especially those with fewer opportunities.
- c) Maximise the impact of Safe Education in different educational communities and environments (e.g. schools, associations, policy-making level, general population);
- d) Support the development of a community through which relevant stakeholders will:
 - Get access to general information related to school engagement, Safe Education and best practices identified by the project.
 - Get access to information on replication and advancement of good educational practices on Safe Education.
 - Share their own experience and good practices on this issue.
 - Promote the co-creation of an inclusive educational culture among the participating members.

2. Tailoring the communication and dissemination activities on the project

The distinctive features of the project will be highlighted through a tailored approach to dissemination. The core elements of the project's research and activities are the 4 ecological and social pillars: safe learning, safe teaching, safe school, safe education. Communication and dissemination activities therefore will start from these guiding elements to structure the progressive involvement of stakeholders.

The Pillars allow us to define the general contents of the communication and dissemination activities and also the main target groups of these actions:

PILLARS	KEY CONCEPTS	CONTENTS of the DISSEMINATION	TARGET GROUPS
Safe Learning Student's secure attachment	Individual student well-being Emotional security Positive learning process	Stages of the child's development, the learning process, and educational strategies that promote the child's individual well-being	Teachers, educators, schools, scientific community
Safe Teaching Teacher–Student attachment	Positive relationship with the teacher Trust, support and mutual respect	Relational aspects of teaching, classroom management dynamics, inclusive teaching models	Teachers, educators, schools, scientific community, families
Safe School School Bonding	School environment; Families; Community; Well-being in the context in which the child grows up	School organisation, work-related stress in schools, family involvement School-family educational alliance, children's well-being and their development process	School directors, Head teachers, Teachers, educators, schools, scientific community, families
Safe Education	Policy action Advocacy Attention of the entire community to the needs of children	Educational policies: actions for the involvement of policy makers, public events and raising awareness in society of the need to prevent early school leaving with measures that also consider the	Policy makers and authorities, European policy makers, NGOs and

		well-being of children.	advocacy organisations, General public
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Table 1 – Tailored contents of dissemination

The contents of the communication and dissemination will also adapt to the different stages of the project implementation and will support the actions in the different Work Packages in a collaborative approach:

- **WP1 – LETS CARE: Building up a community:**

The connection between the two WPs is very important, since the creation of a community strongly rely on an effective communication with the target groups. The communication and dissemination activities of the first year will be mostly addressed to support the actions of this WP and in the following years, to keep engaged and motivated the participants to the Network.

- **WP2 – Theorization and characterization:**

After the finalisation of the theoretical model, the results of this WP will be communicated to the educational scientific community with specific actions (detailed in the following pages) that will raise the interest about the project. The activities will start in the second year and will be supported by the results of the other WPs.

- **WP3 – Data collection and analysis:**

The communication and dissemination activities can support the implementation of this WP in two ways: facilitating the recruiting of the stakeholders for the data collection and disseminate the results of the analysis among the educational scientific community. The support to this WP actions will start in the first year of the project, with a stronger commitment during the second (for the ethnographies and the quantitative data collection).

- **WP4 – Designing and developing diagnosis and intervention tools:**

The connection of this technical WP with WP6 is mostly related to the communication and dissemination of the results among the scientific community and the technical stakeholders from the second half of the third year of the project.

- **WP5 – Testing, validation, and uptake:**

As for WP3, the activities of communication and dissemination can support the recruitment of the participants to the validation phase starting from M30. Furthermore, the results of the testing will be widely communicated in the final months of the project.

- **WP6 – Policy recommendations and advocacy. Dissemination, exploitation, and communication**

The communication and dissemination activities will be fundamental since the beginning of the project to raise awareness of decision makers, educative staff, and families on the importance of a safe environment of the well-being and academical success of the children. This will ensure a positive acceptance of the Policy Recommendations.

3. Co-creation process in the framework of Communication and Dissemination

Co-creation is one of the founding aspects of LET'S CARE project and refers to the collaborative integrated process where project partners and key stakeholders jointly contribute with ideas, their expertise and insights to shape the effective project's outcomes. This participatory approach ensures that diverse perspectives are fully included into the research. Considering the communication and dissemination of the project's contents, this open collaboration ensures that messages and means are relevant, accessible, and appealing to the different target groups. This inclusive approach enhances the reach and impact of the project, ensuring it answers to each group's unique needs and perspectives.

In implementing communication and dissemination activities, the co-creation process will initially involve mostly the fieldwork partners and all those representing the main target groups within the consortium. Their direct experience will lead the development of the communication messages and campaigns that will reach the target groups taking into consideration the different languages and school organization in the project's countries. When a communication material will be shared, the consortium will provide feedback and suggestions on how to improve it to better address certain target group. This process of improvement will contribute to produce a more effective communication.

Once a trustful cooperation is built with the main target groups (for example through the Community of Schools or the National Coordination Board), the partners will collect feedback on the initial drafts of the communication materials directly from samples of the target groups, then improving the results according to the comments received. This ensures that the messages are relevant, engaging, and effective in reaching and influencing each group.

The dissemination activities will see a more active participation of the target groups and the partners will implement the events in direct contacts with them, collecting feedback and possibly asking them to be part of the event (for example teachers involved in the research can train their colleagues or school director can present their experience during conferences).

4. Target groups

LET'S CARE project is going to have a future large up-scaling at the local, regional, national and European levels. The participation of all beneficiaries and key stakeholders is fundamental to reach out a critical mass beyond the project's Community of Schools and Network, and ensure deployment, acceptance and replication of Safe Education approach.

Partners have a wide network of contacts at the national and European levels, so the results of studies, research and project activities will be disseminated to a wide and diverse international audience: researchers, NGOs, decision-makers and politicians, professionals in the scientific and educational field, etc. The majority of the beneficiaries are part of European collaboration networks and can disseminate innovations at the transnational level.

The main target groups of the project are:

1. **Students:** Students from challenging contexts, multi-disadvantaged learners, mainstream students.
2. **Students' family environment:** Parents, legal tutors (guardians) and other family members.
3. **Education scientific community:** European universities and research centers in education/pedagogy, tools developers, other related projects.
4. **Teachers' community:** School teachers, educators, other school staff (i.e., school counselors, paraprofessionals, non-teaching staff, etc.), teachers' associations, platforms and networks.
5. **Schools:** Scholar institutions, boards, non-formal educational environments.
6. **Policy makers and authorities (local, regional, national):** Public institutions responsible to assess and approve national and regional education plans.
7. **European policy makers:** Creators and administrators of policy measures to improve educational outcomes.
8. **Non-Governmental Organisations (NGOs) and advocacy organisations**
9. **Citizens, media and general public.**

Detailed tables with the aims of communication and type of information shared for each target group and each category of message is reported in Annex 3.

5. Categories of messages

Dissemination and communication work on four main categories of messages: Awareness, Information, Knowledge, Engagement.

CATEGORY AND DESCRIPTION	TOPICS	TG
<p style="text-align: center;">Awareness</p> <p>LET'S CARE project promotes a change in the educational approach to which the targeted stakeholders have to be introduced.</p> <p>The beneficiaries will implement communication activities to raise and spread awareness about the main topics of the project to the general public, and especially in the educational field.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Educational inclusion of students in vulnerable situations. • Gender equality in education (how gender dynamics may be interacting with safe-teaching competencies). • Role of child attachment, teacher-child attachment relationships and school bonding in school learning and success • Socio-economic benefits of Safe Education for the student and its context (i.e. in terms of their well-being, a better social engagement with their educational communities, the future prospects of children, a better sense of belonging, etc.). • Benefits of participation in the LET'S CARE Network and Community. 	1 - 9
<p style="text-align: center;">Information</p> <p>The second level of communication that has to be implemented during the project, aims at inform people and stakeholders about LET'S CARE work.</p> <p>In other words partners will build awareness regarding the project and its approach, promote the website and the conferences, seminars and other activities related to the project.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Key project aims, results and tools. • Data, methodology and panels of indicators/databases. • Scientific results of the project (e.g. Safe Education holistic model). • LET'S CARE Tools description and piloting results. • LET'S CARE results and socio-economic impact. • European events for teachers and educators. • LET'S CARE events and advocacy actions. 	1 - 9

<p style="text-align: center;">Knowledge</p> <p>The dissemination process has to target directly and involve stakeholders that are in a position to “influence” and “bring about change” within their organizations.</p> <p>These stakeholders should be able to start a change of practice resulting from the adoption of the LET’S CARE approach.</p> <p>It will be important that these target groups and potential stakeholders have a deeper understanding of LET’S CARE project's work and outcomes through:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Direct engagement. • Accessibility to the materials. • Participation in the project's activities process 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Schools’ and students’ needs to the indicators under a “whole organisation approach (school / child / youth-centre / second chance school). • LET’S CARE networks. • Safe Education model and implementation in schools. • Legal, ethical, barriers and requirements for LET’S CARE implementation. • Participative techniques. • Self and peer observation methodologies and tools. • Safe Teaching Practices: guidelines for implementation & advancement & replication. • Safe vocational assessment and guidance tools (e-profile). 	<p>1 - 7</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">Engagement</p> <p>One of the main goals of LET’S CARE is to to promote the students’ educational opportunities by improving the caring dimension of educational systems. So, the Engagement level refers to a change of practice resulting from the adoption of strategies, ideas or approaches developed by the project. The target groups involved at this level will be provided with the right skills, knowledge and understanding of LET’S CARE work in order to achieve real change in their working routine. This will happen through their participation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In the project's activities process. • In local seminars and training courses. • In the workshops and active events. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Facilitate access to educational environment. • Collaborate to make their schools more caring. • Data collection, collaboration, and tools validation processes. • Attraction and engagement in LET’S CARE Network. • Foster interaction among researchers and synergies with other projects. • Attract and incorporate EU and national requirements/needs to the project. • Promote the adoption of policy recommendations at the end of the project. 	<p>1 - 8</p>

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In the use of let's care hub. • In the community of schools (cos). • In the let's care network. 		
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Table 2 - Summary of the categories of messages

5.1 Main messages to be shared

LET'S CARE project main objective is to identify determinants affecting safety relationships as causes of underachievement and school drop out, at four different ecological levels or pillars:

- Individual
- Relational
- Community
- Political

Communication activities implemented during the project development will have a specific message connected to each pillar through the selected target groups:

PILLAR	TARGET GROUP	MAIN MESSAGE TO BE SHARED
INDIVIDUAL level (promoting Safe Learning)	Students and their security in relation with the family, teachers, schools and community.	A child's social satisfaction is crucial for their learning and willingness to stay in school. Children from secure relationships have better social exploration, less peer conflict and more openness to learning. Bonds with families, teachers, schools, and communities provide a sense of socio-emotional security and self-regulation, which are essential for academic achievement and engagement.

<p>RELATIONAL level (promoting Safe Teaching)</p>	<p>Teachers and their relations to students and their families. These relations are conditioned by the school organisation and the community.</p>	<p>Teacher-child relationships are key predictors of academic performance, psychosocial functioning, and motivation/engagement in school, both directly and indirectly, throughout different stages of school life. Attachment theory provides a useful framework for understanding the role of these relationships in development, and research in this area offers new opportunities for studying and intervening with teacher-child relationships.</p>
<p>COMMUNITY level (promoting Safe Schools)</p>	<p>Principals, Academic coordinators, Teaching staff and other school staff, parents' organisations, NGOs</p>	<p>A positive school climate can have several benefits: has a powerful influence on motivation to learn, reduces violence in school, is a protective factor for learning, mitigates the negative impact of socioeconomic context on academic success, contributes to both academic outcomes and personal development and well-being of pupils, reduces student absenteeism.</p>
<p>POLITICAL level (promoting Safe Education)</p>	<p>Policy makers, Social fabric</p>	<p>There has been a shift in the way we approach the issue of students who struggle in school from viewing it as "school failure" to "educational exclusion". This broader concept includes external factors such as personal trajectories, family situations, and economic conditions. To fully understand the problem of early school leaving and academic struggles, we must move beyond the limited context of the school and consider social exclusion as a contributing factor.</p>

Table 3 - Summary of the main messages to be shared according to the pillars

Communication plan

The Communication plan is designed in a way that the tools, channels, and materials will be complementary and mutually reinforcing for delivering the information about LET'S CARE to the target groups. Communication conveys mostly the messages connected to “awareness” and “information”. The messages will be adapted to the target group and the mean used. Communication staff and resources from all partners will be involved to online and face-to-face communication activities directed to the target group.

The communication will be supported by the production of an initial project brochure, a series of fact sheets/leaflets during the different phases of implementation, several short stand-alone videos and/or slideshows. The logo and the visual identity will be included to ensure the distinctiveness and recognition of all project outputs. The contact with mainstream and specialized media will be sought. Press releases and interviews will be organised upon reaching project milestones and important achievements.

All multimedia material produced will be available for download on the project website and other potential distribution channels will be explored as well. An effective and wide-reaching information distribution campaign will be focused on the communication of the project website in which the LET'S CARE Hub will have a presence.

1. Outreach activities

To raise awareness, engage stakeholders and inform about the project's outcomes, various outreach activities will be organized, spanning multiple channels and target audiences. Examples of these activities are:

- **Social Media Campaigns:** Leveraging social media platforms to engage with wider audiences, share project updates, disseminate research findings, and promote discussions around the importance of caring dimensions in educational inclusion and success.
- **Information meetings and Seminars:** Organizing interactive meetings and seminars for educators, school administrators, policymakers, and community leaders, to share insights, good practices, and innovative approaches related to the Safe Education model and its implementation.
- **Press Releases and Media Outreach:** Crafting press releases and establishing relationships with media outlets to amplify the project's messages and achievements. This approach can help reach a wider audience and spark interest in the project among the general public, as well as educational and policy communities.
- **Newsletters and Email Campaigns:** Distributing regular newsletters and email updates to subscribers, providing an overview of the project's progress, research findings, upcoming events, and opportunities for collaboration. This communication channel can help maintain

engagement with interested parties and ensure they remain informed and connected to the project.

- **Public Speaking Engagements:** Participating in relevant conferences, panel discussions and public events as speakers or panellists to share the project's insights, research outcomes and policy recommendations with a diverse audience. These engagements can foster networking opportunities, collaborative partnerships, and increased awareness of the project's aims and successes.

2. Communication materials

The communication materials will follow the LET'S CARE visual identity and will be developed according to the Horizon Europe guidelines. These materials will be developed firstly in English and then translated into different languages when targeting specific educational environments within the partners' countries. All communication products should use a gender-sensitive language.

In communication activities, using more than one language and more than one communication channel may help with the inclusion of different target groups, when possible. Regarding accessibility in social media campaigns, it is recommended to generate materials not only to be read but also to be heard and watched.

The following communication material will support communication purposes and activities and will be available for downloading on the project's website.

2.1. Digital newsletter

Regular newsletters with the latest news about the project, on inclusive education and on promotion of safe relationships in schools will be produced, sent by email, and published through the LET'S CARE HUB. News will be uploaded in the project website, promoting visits and SEO positioning. The newsletter will be also promoted through School Education Gateway (SEG), NobodyLess Community Network and other online communities and networks related to education.

The use of mailing lists of stakeholders will be very useful to:

- Engage different stakeholders in the co-created methodologies gather stakeholders around LET'S CARE Hub.
- Maximise the visibility and impact of the project.

KPIs: ≥12 newsletters, ≥50,000 recipients overall.

2.2. *Promotional videos*

A short video will be created presenting the project and its main goals and future results, in English with subtitles in up to 5 languages. Uploaded to the project website and other social media. During the project, 2 more videos will be created explaining the results achieved.

KPI: ≥3 videos; ≥600 views on YouTube, ≥200 views on Twitter.

Beyond LET'S CARE: video channels active (as corporate channels) and LET'S CARE videos will be kept available.

2.3. *Supporting communication material*

Brochures, leaflets and infographics (in physical and digital format) will be produced and used to communicate with external environments and at public events. Original content (written, visual and audio-visual) will be used to support direct contact with different stakeholders, show overview of the project's aim, progress, and activities.

KPI: 3 brochures/leaflets/infographics, 2,000 downloads of digital versions.

2.4. *Press releases and interviews*

The work with media will include publishing articles in local press and other media at the European, national, and regional levels in occasion of milestones accomplishment and/or project meetings and national workshops. Press releases will be translated into all different languages of the consortium and others relevant for project's outreach. Partners will also work towards interaction with local journalists to arrange interviews and establish a closer relationship with selected media. A final press dossier will be elaborated, outlining all actions and milestones achieved with relevant project data.

KPIs: 8 press releases, 10 interviews.

3. **Communication channels**

LET'S CARE's communication channels are diversified in order to reach as many stakeholders as possible, from the ordinary citizen to scientific and political circles. Depending on the interests of each target group, communication channels employed will be different.

3.1. *LET'S CARE website*

The website of the LET'S CARE project has been created under the domain <https://letsproject.eu/> and a first look at the website can be observed in Annex 4 together with a description of its features. This website will be the main starting point for all communication, exploitation, dissemination, and up-scaling activities. Moreover, the website will contain information on the project, its public

deliverables (with download links when they become available), the partnership, news, and external links of related sites, policy, research, and practice. Although available from month 3 of the project, it will be updated and maintained throughout the project period and sustained for a minimum of 5 years after the project ends.

The website is fully responsive, available on any computer or mobile device.

KPI: 25000 visits, 5000 downloads.

Beyond LET'S CARE: COM, as coordinator, commits to keep active and updated with content the project website

3.2. LET'S CARE Hub

The LET'S CARE Hub is a Content Management System (CMS) tailored for the LET'S CARE stakeholders and community. It is a digital, on-line, open-source, free access, collaborative and participative tool to find all the (relevant LET'S CARE) information, contents, and tools and to further exchange and engage with the project community.

The objectives of the LET'S CARE Hub/CMS are to:

- Facilitate communication and exchange.
- Establish of a lively LET'S CARE community.
- Establish a storage system for the LET'S CARE project products and results.

The Hub will be accessible from M12, an initial description of its elements and features can be found in Annex 5.

KPI: 1000 registered users by the end of the project; 120 involved schools, 100 best practices shared, 5000 downloads of shared resources.

Beyond LET'S CARE: FHV will cede Hub maintenance to COM and POLO. During *flourishing* and *harvesting* phases, possibilities for Hub sponsorships will be sought.

3.3. Social Media

Social Media channels will be created to promote participation of stakeholders and to strengthen the visibility and impact of the project results. Holding an active social media presence will attract the interest of stakeholders and the general public and will serve to make the virtual community grow. Social Media channels will be fed with news, updated content from the website and other contents published by the stakeholders involved in the sector and related to LET'S CARE.

Partners should consider the following aspects in order to hold an active and relevant presence in social media and to provide information of interest to the public and stakeholders:

- Use the hashtag of the project: **#LetsCareProject**
- Take advantage of any audiovisual material to be disseminated in social media channels.
- Participate in the conversation on social media channels.
- Monitor basic data from their own Social Media profiles/accounts.

The following LET'S CARE social media accounts will be/have been activated:

- [Twitter](#) will be used to promote project actions and messages among stakeholders, media and public and to foster networking (@LetsCareProject).
- [Facebook](#) will be used to communicate project actions and messages helping to social awareness (lets care.project).
- [YouTube/ TubEdu.org channels](#) will be used to promote videos connected to the project.
- [LinkedIn /ResearchGate](#) will be used to upload and promote project actions, publications, and messages among policymakers and stakeholders and foster research and professional networking (LinkedIn: Let's Care (Horizon Europe) project).
- [Instagram](#) will be used to reach the Youth mainly by means of pictures and stories (@lets care_horizon_europe).

KPIs: 2,000 followers in 6 networks, > 10,000 overall interactions in social media.

Beyond LET'S CARE: further developments of LET'S CARE innovations and solutions will be posted on corporate accounts of the partners and linked to LET'S CARE accounts to keep them alive.

3.4. Newsletters and mailing

A quarterly newsletter with the latest news about the project, on inclusive education and on promotion of safe relationships in schools will be produced and sent by email. News will be uploaded in the project website, promoting visits and SEO positioning. The newsletter will be also promoted through School Education Gateway (SEG), NobodyLess Community Network and other online communities and networks related to education.

The use of mailing lists of stakeholders will be very useful to:

- Engage different stakeholders in the co-created methodologies gather stakeholders around LET'S CARE Hub.
- Maximise the visibility and impact of the project.

KPIs: ≥12 newsletters, ≥50,000 recipients overall

Beyond LET'S CARE: used to keep members of the network informed about the evolution of the project and its realized activities.

Dissemination plan

Dissemination plan is aimed to ensure the direct and tangible involvement of the target groups in the project and bring them to use the project's results in their daily life. The dissemination plan identifies activities that the partners can implement to convey mostly messages connected to "knowledge" and "engagement". Staff and resources of the partners will be employed to organise and participate in events that can actively involve stakeholders and create the LET'S CARE network. Indeed, one of the main purposes of the dissemination plan is to consider and gather the views of the target groups, according to the co-created approach of the project.

Multiplier events in six project's countries will be organised to maximize the impact of Safe Education in different educational communities and environments. During the events, the organising partner will guarantee accessibility assuring the existence of access ramps to buildings and offering automatic translation and sign language translation in case someone needs it.

Safe Education model and LET'S CARE results will be disseminated in the scientific and academical community through the presence in conferences and the publication of articles. Moreover, partners will organise specific activities at the policy-maker level to advocate the importance of a Safe Learning for all learners, especially those with fewer opportunities.

LET'S CARE events will include specific actions to present gender and diversity findings about the theoretical and practical framework that will have been designed. In this regard, LET'S CARE final event will include a particular lecture about it.

1. Multiplier events organised by the Consortium

LET'S CARE partners will carry out 9 events to disseminate the results of the project at national and European level with the aim of establishing a powerful and solid network of relevant stakeholders in the field of education in Europe. These dissemination events will expand the project's opportunities to improve school and other stakeholders' engagement. Overall, these events can maximize project's social impact.

When feasible, events can be broadcasted via streaming or via consistent postings on the social networks.

Examples of these multiplier events are:

- **International youth forum** (Italy): involving young students from the project's countries. They will work together for 5 days, with facilitators from the consortium, discussing about their conditions and their needs for a Safe educational environment, improving their experiences and competences.
- **International teachers forum** (Italy): held simultaneously to the youth forum. Participant teachers will be representatives of LET'S CARE Schools community, to strengthen contacts

between consortium partners and members of the community and among participants themselves. They will present Safe Teaching practices and share best practices and will be provided with further specific training.

- **LET'S CARE national conferences:** in the second half of the project implementation, with the aim of disseminate LET'S CARE model and project results and training researchers, trainers, facilitators, teachers, counsellors, and boards on the different tools. They will be organized in Italy, Spain, Bulgaria, Portugal, Poland, Lithuania.
- **LET'S CARE Final International Conference:** involving education stakeholders, decision and policy makers, representatives of other European projects. Workshops for teachers, tutors, counsellors, and boards.

KPIs: organising 9 events (3 international, 6 national) during the lifetime of the project.

Beyond LET'S CARE: POLO commits to continue organizing the Verona Youth Forum with LET'S CARE perspective. PROMA will continue organizing Teachers Forum.

2. Participation to events and Networking

Events like national and transnational trainings, conferences, symposia, workshops, special sessions, forums, and other EU Research Initiatives can be considered as the most significant occasions for reaching and engaging the relevant stakeholders, promoting the project in a direct, open, and impactful way. These events are opportunities that facilitate the interaction with the target groups for the dissemination of project results, while promoting solid relationships, increasing the networking, and reaching a larger audience.

The different research results achieved during the project, will be disseminated to different key stakeholders. Thus, partners will dedicate strong efforts in communicating project evolution during different events, fairs and workshops. A detailed list providing some examples of the main events identified as strategic for LET'S CARE project can be found in Annex 6. This list will be periodically updated by the consortium since new events will be identified during the project lifecycle.

KPIs: 15-20 EU events/fairs/workshops attendance

Beyond LET'S CARE: partners participate on an annual basis in 5-7 EU events, workshops and fairs.

3. Clustering with other EU platforms, networks, and initiatives

LET'S CARE consortium will look for synergies with key initiatives at the European and national levels, as well as the evolution of key indicators established by European Commission in the Education and

Training sector. Partners have a strong presence in several European committees and networks, with which they will establish connections and organise workshops, webinars, round tables, among others.

Some examples of these networks are:

- **parENTrepreneurs.eu:** The main aim of this Project is to involve families on entrepreneurship education through ENTRECOMP framework. JEX and IPA participate to this initiative, thus LET'S CARE resources can be promoted.
- **Nobody Less** community network: It is a worldwide community of educational institutions promoting prosocial values. LET'S CARE project and results will be disseminated in this network activities thanks to the participation of POLO, ARID, PRSC, KITE.
- **School Education Gateway:** SEG is a portal of the European Commission that supports schools in planning Erasmus+ projects. SEG includes the European Toolkit for Schools, which supports the exchange of best practices among school practitioners and policymakers. LET'S CARE will disseminate the results and create synergies with the main resources of SEG.

KPIs: 5 joint events workshops, webinar, round tables, panel presentations with other EU initiatives.

Beyond LET'S CARE: presentation of and Erasmus+ projects to sustain and continue LET'S CARE piloting and implementation.

4. Policy and advocacy actions

LET'S CARE partners will implement specific activities to reach the policy-making level to advocate the importance of a Safe Learning environment for all learners, especially those with fewer opportunities.

Some examples of these actions are:

- **Public hearings at European level:** IPA will organize meetings with Directorate General of Education, Youth, Sport, and Culture (DG EAC), and European Parliament Committee on Culture and Education (EP CULT). Final findings of the Youth and Teachers forum will be presented by the participants to the national representatives of DG EAC during the conferences that will be organized in Verona.
- **Policy action at regional/national level:** JEX will work at regional level in the Spanish region of Extremadura to present the findings of the project and the legislative modifications needed to adapt regional education systems. POLO will look for the collaboration of the Veneto Region office of education to advocate a change toward a Safe educational approach.
- **Workshops with policy makers:** the Policy Makers Advisory Board (PMAB) will perform a continuous assessment of the project implementation. This board will facilitate the contact with other policy makers at national, regional, and European level. IPA will mobilise its extensive European network to reach out to policy makers, especially through the European Education Policy Network (EEPN) on Teachers and School Leaders with 30 members from 19

European countries. 5 policy workshops will be organised reaching policy makers from at least 15 countries, leveraging events where they will attend, such as the Annual Conference of the EEPN, or the Assemblies of the European School Heads Association.

- **Other advocacy actions:** advocacy work with other European Parliament Committees, European Economic and Social Committee (EESC), European Committee of the Regions, EAEA Lifelong Learning Interest Group, leading human rights organizations such as Council of Europe, through public consultation, individual meetings, participation at public hearings, and inviting them to LET'S CARE events.

5. Activities addressed to the scientific community

The results achieved during the project implementation will be disseminated to different key scientific communities. Thus, research and academia partners will dedicate strong efforts in participating to scientific community events and in publishing scientific papers with theoretical contributions on Safe Education.

5.1. Participation to scientific conferences and seminars

LET'S CARE partners will participate to conferences at European and global level with the aim of presenting the project results and involving relevant stakeholders and scientific community. An initial plan of the participation to these events can be found in Annex 7.

KPIs: participation in 24 conferences/seminars (8 conferences/partner average).

Beyond LET'S CARE: participation in 18 conferences.

5.2. Scientific publications

Research partners with an extensive record of successful publishing are committed to write articles about the project to strengthen the dissemination in the scientific area. Partners will submit publication in Open Access, High Impact or local journals or they will write informative articles to be published on other mainstream journals about education.

KPIs: 9 scientific publications

Beyond LET'S CARE: 6 publications, as part of COM, AIK, UCP LETS CARE follow-up 2028

Communication and dissemination monitoring

Communication and dissemination activities must be monitored throughout the whole duration of the project in order to assess the involvement of the target groups and the achievement of the project's objectives and KPIs. Each partner will identify among its staff at least one person that will be in charge for monitoring and reporting dissemination and communication activities done by his/her organization. It will be created a team that will meet regularly with the following tasks:

- Monitoring of the communication data collection.
- Keep the coordinator informed.
- Keep the other partners informed.
- Send to the website's / hub's responsables the materials to be published.
- Update the social media channels.
- Create a mailing list database to send information and newsletters.
- Proactively engage with media to rise let's care profile.
- Write and distribute press releases.
- Develop media cooperation with relevant professional journals.

1. Work-plan of the communication and dissemination plan

An initial Gantt diagram has been developed (reported in Annex 8) identifying the main deadline and working period for communication and dissemination activities. The plan will guide the partners and will allow to monitor and plan ahead the activities.

2. Reporting and KPI

Communication and dissemination will be monitored throughout the project lifetime in order to measure the effectiveness of the different channels, tools and activities implemented. This will allow partners to adapt and update communication strategy in order to reach the communication and dissemination objectives. Different sources of information will be used to analyse and measure these aspects:

- 1) **Analytics:** Monitoring measurement tools for LET'S CARE Web, LET'S CARE hub and Social Media channels
- 2) **Attendance to events and workshops:** Monitoring participation through quantitative data and, whenever possible, monitoring satisfaction
- 3) **Impact in Media:** Monitoring impact in online and offline media sources on a continuing basis.

POLO, as work package leader, will produce three reports presenting the impact of the dissemination and communication activities implemented by the consortium. They will be published following the following work-plan:

- After the second year of the project implementation (month 24)
- After the third year of the project implementation (month 36)
- After the fourth year of the project implementation (month 48)

These reports on dissemination and communication activities will also include the feedback and the recommendations emerging from the analysis of monitoring process. Analysis of dissemination and communication channels, tools and activities will facilitate the updating of the communication and dissemination strategy to reach the foreseen objectives. The detailed table with the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) that will be monitored for Communication and Dissemination can be found in Annex 9.

3. Communication and dissemination data collection

All dissemination and communication activities will be reported, during the lifetime of the project, in a specific table (Annex 10), in order to facilitate the Work Package leader to produce annual reports and to monitor the achievement of the KPIs. In order to give a proof of their declared activities the partners have to collect pictures or photos or signatures on attendance sheets or videos or links and make them available in case of review.

Part C - EXPLOITATION STRATEGY AND IPR

1. Introduction

The exploitation of results is a critical moment in any research and innovation project because it focuses on the effective utilization of the outcomes generated by the project. Exploitation builds upon dissemination activities to create real-world value and impact.

Exploitation encompasses the various strategies, actions and processes that enable a project's outputs to be transformed into beneficial and tangible solutions for targeted audiences and stakeholders.

The primary aim of exploitation is to optimise the value and impact of the project's results by leveraging the research findings, intellectual property, and innovative solutions to address pressing challenges and needs or contribute to social progress. This process involves identifying the project's most valuable assets and determining the most effective ways to share, promote, and implement them in relevant contexts.

2. The exploitation social dimension

Exploitation refers to a set of core values that emphasize the importance of collaboration, transparency, inclusivity, and sustainability. These values ensure that the project's results are accessible to a wide range of stakeholders and that the benefits derived from the project are equitably distributed and long-lasting. The exploitation plan of LET'S CARE will consider not only the aspects of intellectual property and the exploitation of the results. In light of the important social objectives of the project, the consortium members will also develop a plan to ensure exploitation for the benefit of society.

The social dimensions of exploitation play a vital role in amplifying the project's outcomes and fostering a lasting influence on communities, stakeholders, and end-users. In the context of social exploitation, the focus is on leveraging the project's results to address societal challenges, improve the quality of life and contribute to the greater public good. The social aspects of the exploitation of LET'S CARE results will take various forms, such as enhancing public awareness, informing policymaking, fostering collaborations, or supporting capacity building. By prioritizing the social aspects of exploitation, LET'S CARE aims to generate a ripple effect that extends beyond its immediate beneficiaries and stakeholders, contributing to benefit communities and fostering social progress. The social exploitation of project results seeks to create a sustainable, lasting impact that goes beyond the project's lifespan and resonates with a broader audience, ensuring that the fruits of research and innovation are accessible, relevant, and beneficial to all.

3. Exploitation Strategy and IPR management

An ad-hoc methodology has been designed to develop the Exploitation Strategy for LET'S CARE project, following a step-by-step approach which, in its successive stages, includes the generation of exploitation strategy for the key results identified and the definition of an IP (Intellectual Property) management strategy plan.

The following figure shows this step-by-step approach:

Figure 1 - Step by step approach of the Let's care exploitation strategy

The exploitation strategy requires, at a preliminary stage, to identify the most promising results and to carry out a functional analysis of each of the identified key results. This analysis will ensure that the project delivers results that match the purpose for which they have been designed. At a second stage, the potential of each exploitable result will be evaluated, establishing the preliminary strategy for those results that can be exploited by the members of the consortium. According to the definition of the potential results, the project will generate an exploitation strategy. They will be the backbone of the Exploitation Plan of the LET'S CARE Project. In this sense, the partners will require implementing specific IP strategies (patents, utility models, etc.) in order to preserve their foreground (individual or joint ownership scenarios) and focused on defining how the results will be exploited (further internal research, collaborative research, licensing, internal product development, joint venture, etc.) according to their technology maturity at the end of the project.

4. Schedule of Exploitation Strategy

The Exploitation strategy has been planned along the duration of the project as shown in the following figure.

Figure 2 – Exploitation and IPR management Gantt

Each of the stages related to the Exploitation Strategy are described in the following sections.

4.1. Stage 1. Definition of IP Management Plan

During the first year of the LET'S CARE project, partners will begin executing the IP management strategy outlined in section 5, starting with strategies for handling background and foreground IP as defined in the Grant and Consortium Agreements. This period aims to map out the IPR management's main phases, pinpointing each consortium member's specific background and foreground. As the project progresses, identified exploitable results will be refined. When these outcomes reach maturity, strategies for preserving knowledge ownership using suitable IP tools will be clearer. Additionally, new exploitable results may emerge from the technical work packages, to be managed according to the project's IP strategy. All findings will be incorporated into the IP Management Plan, with the final document included in deliverable D6.4, due in Month 48.

4.2. Stage 2. Identification of Key Results

In Stage 2 of the LET'S CARE project's Exploitation Strategy, a screening procedure will be established to identify potentially commercially viable technologies, products, or services developed within the project. This stage builds on preliminary results outlined in Section 2.2 of Part B (Annex 1 to the Grant Agreement), serving as a foundation for Stage 3. A key component is a questionnaire distributed to all partners, designed to capture both anticipated results and any unforeseen outcomes identified by partners. This stage also considers jointly owned results specified in the Consortium Agreement. Additionally, ongoing monitoring will ensure the identification and analysis of any new results with social potential, updating the selection for future evaluation in the Exploitation Plan.

The procedure consists of the following 3 steps:

- Step 1. Gathering information of identified key results: Partners are provided with an Excel template by ZIC, designed to collect detailed information on each identified result. This template will have multiple sheets corresponding to the different results identified for potential exploitation. Partners who have already pinpointed results with exploitation potential will fill out this template to facilitate later evaluation. If new results emerge from unforeseen project developments and are essential for achieving the project's goals, the identifying partner(s) will add a new sheet to the template and complete the same questionnaire for these additional results. Scientific outputs will be clearly defined, including research papers, methodologies, algorithms, prototypes or any other intellectual asset.
- Step 2. Analysis of key results potential for exploitation: ZIC will review completed templates for initial analysis and determine if additional information is needed. They will then identify results with potential for commercialization based on template data. These results will be presented to the General Assembly for discussion and approval. Based on feedback, ZIC may revise the list of key results, making necessary inclusions, exclusions, or modifications to reflect their exploitation viability. During this analysis, the mechanism through which scientific knowledge will be transferred to stakeholders involved, would be defined. This mechanism can include training sessions, workshops, documentation, or other forms of knowledge dissemination.
- Step 3. Monitoring of new results and list update: ZIC will make a monitoring work with every partner, all along the first Reporting Period, in order to gather and analyse any new result with exploitation potential which may be identified. This will permit to update the selection of key results that will be evaluated in further stages of the Exploitation Plan process.

4.3. Stage 3. Evaluation of Key Ideas

The exploitation potential of the results generated in LET'S CARE project will be evaluated, in order to identify business ideas and develop business plans for each of them. The business potential will be assessed by a “scoring tool” envisaged considering the following aspects:

- Strength of the key idea (main advantages of the new solution, comparison with similar references of competitors, level of maturity of your innovation);
- Social acceptance-related issues;
- Target market and customer-related issues

As a result of this evaluation, a preliminary definition of the possible exploitation routes will be made, considering the target market of each result.

4.4. Stage 4. Exploitation strategy generation

As described in Section 2.2 of Part B (Annex 1 to GA), the backbone of LET'S CARE exploitation strategy is based on two different approaches fully integrated: a joint and individual exploitation plans. Unlike standalone strategies, these individual exploitation plans are intricately linked to a joint exploitation plan, which will be developed, fostering collaboration and alignment among participating organizations. This integrated approach ensures that the individual plans collectively contribute to the overarching goals defined in the joint strategy. As part of this process, organizations will identify synergies and connections with others through the joint exploitation plan. This collaborative effort aims to maximize the impact of exploitation activities by leveraging the strengths of each organization.

The exploitation plans will be based on the conclusions and information obtained in all the previous stages of this exploitation strategy, and particularly, on the key idea studies generated in the Stage 3. This stage will develop exploitation strategy propositions for results identified with high potential, setting the groundwork for future plans. These models will align with each partner's broader exploitation strategies within their organizations. Utilizing strategies like Lean Canvas and Exploitation Workshops, coordinated by ZIC, all partners will contribute to generating specific knowledge. The approach, inspired by Lean Canvas methodology—a concise document encapsulating key aspects like value proposition, target market, and revenue streams—aims to tailor each exploitation result to the nature of the key idea. Some important points to be considered in the approach inspired by the “Exploitation Canvas” overview is reported in Annex 11.

4.5. Stage 5. Updated IP Management Plan

Once the business models associated of the exploitable results are well defined, the knowledge generated will be preserved following a specific IP mechanism identified by the implementation of the IP management strategy. during this Stage it will be carried out the mapping of existing patents related to the knowledge generated for those results could be protected by a patent mechanism: Assessment of the knowledge produced and general recommendation for protection. As a result of this, in the month 48 it will be included an updated IP Management Plan within deliverable D6.6.

4.6. Stage 6. Networking with Projects & Initiatives

The objective of this stage is to seek for synergies with other projects & initiatives. To achieve this, the following actions will be carried out:

- Alignment with other Exploitation Strategies from other projects & initiatives.
- Participation in joint events, workshops, and fairs with other projects & initiatives.

- Generating synergies with potential business stakeholders (providers, clients, investors, etc.).
- Discussion how ongoing maintenance, updates and further development of scientific outputs will be addressed after project conclusion.

5. IPR Management Strategy

The IPR management strategy for LET'S CARE project includes the following contents:

- A set of the most relevant definitions, procedures, and agreements (included in the CA), that regulate the IP management within LET'S CARE consortium.
- Starting from the defined background, a mapping of existing patents and potentially IPR overlapping for the future Foreground.
- An assessment of the knowledge generated in the project.
- A proposition of optimal IPR protection options, in line with the obtained results.
- A mapping of existing relevant standards and of standards in development.
- Considerations with regards to the standardisation strategy.

The contents of this preliminary version of the IPR Management Strategy have been elaborated considering on the European IPR helpdesk methodology. In the present version of D6.2, the IPR Management Strategy is at a preliminary stage, where the methodology is defined, and some contents but not all are available. The complete version of this document will be delivered within the final D6.6 delivery, in month 48 of the project.

6. Mapping of existing patents and potentially IPR overlapping for the future Foreground

To secure the LET'S CARE project's operational freedom, it's crucial to analyse existing patents for potential overlap with anticipated outputs. From the outset, surveillance is essential to identify any protected designs or technologies that might intersect with the project's results, also aiding in recognizing beneficial technologies or knowledge. Partners must engage IPR-specialized personnel for this purpose. In joint development scenarios, prompt communication of any patent overlaps is vital for timely strategic decisions. This can be facilitated through work package meetings, synchronization meetings, or Executive Board meetings, ensuring effective information dissemination.

7. Assessment of the knowledge generated in the project (Foreground)

Any result generated in the project, with potential of exploitation, will be correctly assessed in order to check such potential and analyse exploitation routes and optimal protection measures, when appropriate. To do so, a first action to take is to create a procedure to efficiently identify and assess the results generated. In this sense, the Stage 2 of the Exploitation Strategy aims at identifying the results with exploitation potential, through the complementation of a simple questionnaire that includes useful information to make a first assessment of the exploitation potential, market suitability, and technical and non-technical barriers. The assessment of the exploitation potential of such results will be performed in the Stage 3 of the exploitation strategy.

8. First definition of IP results' protection possibilities

Some results to be generated in LET'S CARE project could be subjected to protection actions, to ensure an effective exploitation. This will be assessed once such results are generated. Each partner will decide about the possible protection of its results, as well as about which protection action is the most suitable. Regarding joint ownership results, protection issues will be agreed between the partners involved and will be included in the joint ownership agreements. The choice of the most suitable form of IP protection, as well as the duration and geographical coverage will depend on the results at stake, as well as on the business plans for their exploitation and legitimate interests of consortium partners.

A proposed choice of the most suitable form of IP protection according to the type of intellectual property is next offered.

	Patent	Utility Model	Industrial Design	Copyright	Trade Mark	Confidential Information
Inventions	X	X				X
Software	X	X		X		X
Scientific article				X		
Design of a Product			X	X	X	
Name of a technology/product					X	
Know How	X	X				X
Website			X	X	X	X

Figure 3 - A reference of the most suitable form of IP protection according to the type of intellectual property

A proposition of optimal IPR protection options, in line with the obtained results, will be developed in later stages, and will be included in the final version of this deliverable.

Some recommendations made by the IPR Helpdesk regarding results that are not protected are included in Annex 12.

Annex 1 – Internal communication: processes, structure and tools

1. Real-Time communication

The project's work plan foresees 3 face-to-face meetings of the General Assembly in which all the partners have to be present. The first kick off meeting has been held in Madrid on 21-22 October 2022. To keep the regular monitoring of the project's implementation, the Coordinator will plan Technical Committee meetings with the representatives of the WP leaders and all the partners involved in the actions to be discussed. The aim of these meetings is to collect information on the project progresses. The Technical Committee will meet bimonthly during the first year of the project, and then the periodicity of these meetings will be reviewed and rescheduled according to the progresses. The meetings will be held online, they will be recorded, and the minutes will be shared with the whole consortium in order to keep all the partners informed.

The project coordinator or the WP leaders can organize synchronization meetings when the implementation process requires direct dialogue, shared decision or common understanding on the project issues. The synchronization meetings can involve the whole WP, different WPs for a shared action or specific partners.

To facilitate the organization of the online meetings POLO has created a specific LET'S CARE account in the teleconference service Huddle.team. The data of the account and the instructions on how to use the service have been shared with the partners. The account can host up to 1000 users, it has a time attendance reporting system, it can record and store the meetings and can allow different kinds of call (e.g. assembly, lesson, Q&A sessions, etc.). A specific training and video instructions have been provided to the consortium to facilitate the use of this tool.

2. Asynchronous communication

The main part of the internal communication will be asynchronous, through exchange of emails. Since the beginning of the project, it has been created a database of internal contacts to facilitate the communication and to ensure that all the interested persons are properly reached. All the partners have filled a table indicating name and email of the staff involved in the project and in which WP each person will work. The table also indicates the WP leaders and the reference persons for administrative and budget issues. When a person has to send an email to all the staff working in a certain WP, they can select the filters on the table and copy all the resulting addresses. The table is accessible to all the persons registered to the project's Nextcloud (see below the details) and is regularly updated with the changes of the staff.

To maintain clear, professional, and efficient communication it is useful to follow guidelines for effective emailing practices:

- *Use Clear and Specific Subject Lines:* Ensure that the subject line accurately reflects the content of the email. Include the project name and a brief descriptor of the email's purpose (e.g., "Let's Care - Monthly Report Submission Reminder").
- *Identify Yourself Clearly:* It's preferable to include a signature with full name, position, organization, and contact information at the end of your emails for easy identification and reference.
- *Address the Right Recipients:* Use the proper names from the distribution lists. Use 'To' for primary recipients who need to take action, 'Cc' (carbon copy) for those who need to be kept informed.
- *Avoid Email Overload:* Before sending an email, consider if all the addresses have to receive that information (e.g. some answers might be addressed just to the sender, to the WP leader and the coordinator).
- *Be Concise and to the Point:* Keep emails brief and focused. Clearly state the purpose of the email in the first few sentences. Use bullet points or numbered lists for easy readability.
- *Respect Confidentiality:* Do not share sensitive or confidential information without authorization. Be cautious when forwarding emails and ensure that all recipients are intended and appropriate.
- *File Naming and Attachments:* Use descriptive file names and include relevant attachments only. Ensure files are virus-free and compatible with commonly used software.
- *Use Professional Language:* Maintain a professional tone in all communications. Be polite and respectful, even in challenging situations.
- *Prioritize Responsiveness:* Aim to respond to emails within a specified timeframe (e.g., 48 hours). If a detailed response is needed, acknowledge the email and specify when a full response will follow.

3. Shared digital workspace

Integrate shared digital workspace into an internal communication process significantly enhances collaboration and accessibility to the resources. The shared digital workspace is a cloud storage solution, that serves as a centralized platform where documents, files, and project-related resources can be stored, shared, and accessed by team members regardless of their location. This centralized

access facilitates seamless collaboration, as all team members can work on documents simultaneously, track revisions, and share feedback in real time. By ensuring that the latest versions of files are always available, a shared digital workspace minimizes the risks of data losses and information discrepancies, which are common challenges in European projects.

POLO provided a Nextcloud space within its secured server. Nextcloud operates by providing a secure, private cloud space where users can upload, manage, and share files through a web interface or desktop and mobile apps. Users can create folders to organize documents, set permissions for file access, and collaborate to the project's documents. Additionally, the platform's ability to integrate with various communication tools and office suites enhances the efficiency of the internal communication process, allowing for a smoother exchange of ideas and information and enabling team members to stay aligned with project goals and timelines. A specific training and video instructions have been provided to the consortium to facilitate the use of this tool.

Each partner has provided the list of name and emails of the staff working in the project. Specific accounts have been created in the cloudspace and each person has received the permission to access LET'S CARE folder. This process of registration allows the user access controls, ensuring that sensitive project information remains secure. The list of users will be regularly updated according to the changes of the staff involved.

Annex 2 - External Communication and Dissemination potential of the consortium

Potential quantitative impact of the consortium on the target groups

Partner	Students	Families	Educ. Scient. Comm.	Teachers	Schools	Policy Makers	Eu. Policy Makers	NGOs & Advocacy Org.	Citizen	Total
AIK	3000	90	110		61					3261
ARID	20	20	2	100	25	2		5	100	274
CID			15			20	8	60	160	263
COM			45	1000	300	10		10		1365
FHV			4							4
IPA	Potentially millions	Potentially millions	500		Potentially hundreds	TBD	TBD	TBD	TBD	500
JEX	1000 +	1000+	TBD	TBD	500 +	TBD				2502
KITE	3700	2000	320		26	16		10	5000	11072
POLO			10	4500 +	4000 +	30	2	20	1000	9562
PROMA			10 +	1000	10 +	10 +		10		1040
PRSC	100	20	5	300	20	60		2		507
UCP		50	20	1000	22	4			50000	51096
Total	7820	2181	1042	7900	4964	152	10	117	56260	81446

Table 4 – Potential quantitative impact on the target groups per partner

Potential quantitative impact of the general communication

Partner	Newsletters	Social Media	Total
AIK	3753	10000	13753
ARID	500	1000	1500
CID		6000	6000

COM	5000	4000	9000
FHV	1000	1000	2000
IPA	TDB	TBD	0
JEX		760	760
KITE		10000	10000
POLO	5000	700	5700
PROMA	1000	7000	8000
PRSC	200	20	220
UCP	200		200
Total	16653	40480	57133

Table 5 – Potential quantitative impact of the general communication

Networks that can potentially contribute to the sharing of information

Partner	Affiliation to networks
AIK	7
ARID	2
CID	60
COM	20
IPA	3
JEX	3
KITE	4
POLO	5
PRSC	2
UCP	50
Total	156

Table 6 – Affiliation to networks that can contribute to widen the communication

Annex 3 – Type of information shared with each target group

Dissemination and Communication strategy is designed (and will be implemented) taking into consideration each typology of target groups, their characteristics and importance and the type of information and main message to share with them.

All communicative actions should make visible and give the floor to different vulnerable groups.

Language will be reviewed keeping people with disabilities in mind so as to be understandable and clear and considering easy to read standards.

TARGET GROUP	AIMS of the COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES
1. Students	To involve them in the project, in the research and in the community
2. Students' families	
3. Education scientific community	To inform about the research
4. Teachers' community, 5. Schools	To involve them in the project, in the research, in the community of schools and in the Network
6. Policy makers and authorities (local, regional, national)	To promote Safe School Policy, co-creation of the policy proposal
6. European policy makers	To promote Safe School Policy
7. NGOs and advocacy organizations, 8. EU citizens	To involve them in the project, in the research and in the community

Table 7 - Summary of the aim for each target group

CAT.	TYPE OF INFORMATION	TARGET GROUPS								
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
AWARENESS	Educational inclusion of students in vulnerable situations	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
	Role of attachment in learning, importance of school bonding in school success	X	X	X	X					
	Socio-economic benefits of safe education for the student and its context	X	X		X	X				X
	Benefits of participation in the LETS CARE Network and Community			X	X	X			X	
INFOR MATION	Key project aims, results and tools	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X

	Data, methodology and panels of indicators/databases			X		X		X				
	Scientific results of the project: Safe Education holistic model			X	X	X	X			X		
	LETS CARE Tools description and piloting results			X	X	X	X	X	X			
	LETS CARE results and socio-economic impact									X	X	X
	European events for teachers and educators			X	X	X	X					
	LETS CARE events and advocacy actions				X						X	
KNOWLEDGE	LETS CARE networks: Hub, communities	X	X	X		X						
	Participative techniques			X	X	X						
	Self and peer observation methodologies and tools					X						
	Safe teaching practices: guidelines for implementation & advancement & replication					X	X					
	Safe vocational assessment and guidance tools (e-portfolio)	X	X			X	X					
	Schools' needs to the indicators under a whole school approach	X	X			X	X					
	Safe Education model and implementation in schools	X	X			X	X					
	Legal, ethical, barriers and requirements for LETS CARE implementation					X	X	X	X			
ENGAGEMENT	Facilitate access to educational environments						X		X	X		
	Collaborate to make their schools safer	X	X	X	X	X						
	Data collection, collaboration, and tools validation processes	X	X			X		X	X			

Attraction and engagement in LET'S CARE network			X	X	X			X
Foster interaction among researchers and synergies with other projects			X				X	X
Attract and incorporate EU and national requirements/needs to the project			X			X	X	
Promote the adoption of policy recommendations at the end of the project						X	X	

Table 8 – Types of information shared with the target groups

Annex 4 – LET’S CARE website

Figure 4 - Project's website

The actual structure is as follows:

- **Home page** : This page contains a general description of the project, its aims and the Consortium
- **Project menu**: with four subheadings from the drop-down menu:
 - *Community* with information about the LET'S CARE dynamisation bodies and structures.
 - *Research* presents the details on the LET'S CARE theoretical model and its methodology.
 - *Partners introduces* the partners of the project
 - *Resources* has two subheadings available from the drop-down menu, "Project Resources" where deliverables produced in the scope of the LET'S CARE project will be uploaded, and "External Resources" where visitors can see other freely accessible, relevant resources in the topic of the project, not developed in the scope of LET'S CARE
- **Hub**: this menu point takes the user directly to the LET'S CARE Hub
- **Newsroom**: this menu point has five subheadings linking to:

- *Latest news*: all the recent posts uploaded on the website;
- *Events*: announcements or descriptions of the events related to the project organized or attended by the Consortium
- *Media corner*: communication, information and promotion materials like videos, fliers, infographics
- *Newsletter*: posting of the LET'S CARE newsletters
- *Training courses*: presentations of the training courses related to the project organized by the partners
- **Privacy policy**: this section presents, in two subheadings, information related to the security and confidentiality issues on the website and on the social media.

Annex 5 – LET’S CARE Hub

The elements and features of the LET’S CARE Hub consists of:

- A library containing public deliverables, newsletters, publications, training material.
- Documentation of data collection (methodology, ethical protocols, questionnaires, datasets).
- Safe education database of policies, programs, and projects.
- Project tools.
- Intranet, internal documentation and minutes, agenda, calendar, links to external tools.
- Data collection platform (quantitative data).
- Interaction space (project target groups).
- Registration through the project website.
- The let’s care hub gives access to approved let’s care contacts and hub subscribers to do data uploads and downloads.

Annex 6 – Examples of dissemination events the partners will organize and participate to

WORKSHOPS	
Participation to Life-long learning festival	During this kind of event is possible to organize workshops for students, teachers, educators, social mentors, third age university students
Study days	These events will be organized by the partners to support the teachers delve into practical applications on pedagogical methodologies and educational strategies related to the pillars of the project
Specific workshop on LET'S CARE approach	These events will be organized by the partners to support the teachers delve into practical applications on pedagogical methodologies and educational strategies related to the pillars of the project
EVENTS	
World Teachers' Day	It is held annually to celebrate all teachers around the globe. It commemorates the anniversary of the adoption of the 1966 ILO/UNESCO Recommendation concerning the Status of Teachers, which sets benchmarks regarding the rights and responsibilities of teachers, and standards for their initial preparation and further education, recruitment, employment, and teaching and learning conditions.
National Events of the Observatory for the Integration	The organization includes representatives of the ministries of education, interior, foreign

of Migrant Pupils	affairs and social policies as well as of associations operating in the sector and school institutions.
Participation at the European Research & Innovation Days	It is the European Commission's annual flagship Research and Innovation event, bringing together policymakers, researchers, entrepreneurs and the public to debate and shape the future of research and innovation in Europe and beyond.
Participation to Scientists' Night - Pedagogical Research Section	The European Researchers' Night is a Europe-wide public event, which displays the diversity of science and its impact on citizens' daily lives in fun, inspiring ways.
MEETINGS	
Participation to Atmosphere Future week	It is an annual meeting with NGOs, Teachers, Employers, Local Government, Regional Inspectorates of Education
ASSEMBLIES	
Participation to Assemblies of the European School Heads Association	
Participation to Biennial Parent Summit	This event is organized by IPA.

Table 9– Examples of dissemination events listed per type

Annex 7 – Initial plan for the participation to conferences and events addressed to the education scientific community

CONFERENCE	DESCRIPTION of the EVENT	PLACE	DATE	PARTNER PRESENTING	RESULT PRESENTED
Annual international conference on education	Yearly international conference organized by POLO in Verona presenting innovation in education and pedagogical research, gathering experts and project from all Europe. In 2023 the subject will be "Peace as Educational value", in 2024 education to prosociality.	Verona, Italy	December 2023 // April 2024	POLO	Introduction to the project's pillars and objectives Strategies and methodologies of a Safe Teaching
European Network for Social and Emotional Competence conference	The ENSEC conference focuses on Social and Emotional Learning. The 2024 conference's subject is "Social Emotional Learning and Lifetime Achievement"	Chania, Greece	September, 2024	UCP – AIK	Systematic Literature Review focused on the role of the relationship with parents and peers on school engagement, academic achievement, and early school dropout.
European Association for Research on Learning and Instruction conference	The theme of the EARLI conference in 2025 is "Realising Potentials through Education: Shaping the Minds and Brains for the Future"	Graz, Austria	August, 2025	UCP	to be defined

European Conference on Educational Research (ECER)	The aim of the 'European Conference on Educational Research' is to create an inclusive platform for initiating, reporting, discussing, and promoting high quality educational research, that not only acknowledges its own context but also recognises wider, transnational contexts with their social, cultural and political similarities and differences. It is organized annually.	Nicosia, Cyprus	August, 2024	to be defined	to be defined
International Attachment conference	The "International Attachment Conference" stands out as one of the most prestigious international events in the field of attachment. It attracts and invites renowned professionals as speakers. This distinguished gathering provides a privileged space for knowledge dissemination, networking, and learning about the latest cutting-edge advances in attachment research and practice.	Vienna, Austria	November, 2024	ARID	General dissemination of the project
Teacher Education Policy in Europe conference.	"Innovation in teacher education: Sustainable change & evaluating impact at macro, meso and micro level." Conference provokes to think about the impact of innovation in and on teacher education by exploring the different possible typologies, outcomes, and processes of innovation at the light, mostly, of digitalisation, internalisation, and sustainable development challenges.	Aix-en-Provence, France	March, 2024	UIK	Data collection with teachers results (WP3)

European Research Network about Parents in Education conference.	The main purposes of ERNAPE are information exchange between researchers and organisations, research collaboration, providing arenas for analysis and reflection on parents in education, stimulating awareness of the field of parents in education among researchers, educational authorities and stakeholders, including parents themselves, and supporting young researchers in the field of parents in education.	Verona, Italy	2025	UIK	to be defined
Bulgaria National Pedagogical conference on inclusive education.	The annual conference of the Center for Inclusive Education is an annual forum during which we present and discuss current topics and trends in the field of inclusive education in Bulgaria and around the world.	Varna, Bulgaria	July-September 2024	KITE ltd	Introducing Let's Care's aims, HUB, Community of Schools, the national and international partnership
Seminars of Young Scientists - Open Science for Open Education.	Regularly held Interdisciplinary Doctoral Forum (since 2016) of the Training Center at the BAS, - intended for doctoral students studying at the BAS, VU and other scientific organizations, aimed at providing young people with an opportunity to share their scientific ideas, to encourage interdisciplinary thinking, to support the exchange of scientific knowledge and communication with colleagues.	Kyustendil, Bulgaria	April, 2024	KITE ltd	Presentation of the objectives of Let's Care, The research framework and the international partnership.
Annual conference of Bulgaria Ministry of Education	It is an annual conference about Knowledge and innovation, E-learning, Higher Education, Scientific researches, Socialisation of youth in contemporary society, Education, individual and society.	Sofia, Bulgarian	to be defined	KITE ltd	to be defined

EduConference for teachers and IT experts	This yearly conference, organized by the Macedonian teachers' association "Friend of Education", gathers once a year hundreds of teachers and promotes innovation in education in different fields.	Skopje, R. of North Macedonia	to be defined	be POLO	to be defined
Parent Summit	The flagship event of IPA held biennially, venue is different every time	to be defined	to be defined	IPA	to be defined
ESHA Biennial Conference	The flagship event of the European School Heads Association held biennially, venue is different every time	to be defined	to be defined	IPA	to be defined
ATEE conference	Annual conference of the teacher education universities	to be defined	to be defined	IPA	to be defined
ECPR conference	Annual conference on policy research	to be defined	to be defined	IPA	to be defined
ICE-International Conference on Engineering, Technology, and Innovation	The MDTWeek will explore a wide range of digital transformation areas including Health, Manufacturing, Maritime, Smart Cities and Energy, unlocking the Digital Transformation potential.	Maidera, Portugal	June, 2024	FHV	Development of a flexible and agile requirement engineering method. The method is applied for requirement analysis of the Let's Care Work Package 4.

Table 10– Examples of conferences the consortium is planning to participate in

Annex 8 – Communication and dissemination Gantt

Annex 9 - Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for Communication and Dissemination

AREA	KPIs
Promotional videos	3 promotional videos created (2 by M24, 3 by M36) 600 views on Youtube (200 by M24, 600 by M36) 200 views on Twitter (80 by M12, 200 by M36)
Communication material	3 brochures/leaflet/infographic (2 by M24, 3 by M48) 2.000 downloads/views of digital versions (800 by M24, 1500 by M36, 2000 by M48)
LETS CARE website	25.000 visits (4000 by M12, 10000 by M24, 17000 by M36, 25000 by M48) 5.000 downloads (1000 by M24, 2000 by M36, 5000 by M48)
LETS CARE Hub	1.000 users (200 by M24, 600 by M36, 1000 by M48) 120 involved schools (20 by M12, 80 by M36, 120 by M48) 100 best practices shared (20 by M24, 80 by M36, 100 by M48) 5000 downloads of shared resources (1000 by M24, 2500 by M36, 5000 by M48)
Social Media channels	2.000 followers in 6 networks (Twitter, Facebook, Viber, Youtube, LinkedIn, ResearchGate) (400 by M12, 1000 by M24, 1700 by M36, 2000 by M48) 10.000 overall interactions (1000 by M12, 4000 by M24, 7000 by M36, 10000 by M48)
Newsletter and mailing campaign	12 quarterly newsletters 50.000 recipients (8000 by M12, 25000 by M24, 40000 by M36, 50000 by M48) 1.000 subscriber to the mailing lists (300 by M12, 600 by M24, 900 by M36, 1000 by M48)
Congress and conferences	15/20 EU events/fairs/workshops 24 scientific conferences/seminars 5 joint events workshops, webinar, round tables, panel presentations with other EU initiatives

	2 public hearings at DG EAC, EP CULT
Workshops	5 workshops with policy makers (2 by M36, 5 by M48)
Dissemination events	9 LETS CARE events (2 by M24, 6 by M36, 9 by M48) 2 awareness campaign (1 by M24, 2 by M48)
Press	8 press releases (2 by M24, 5 by M36, 8 by M48) 10 interviews (2 by M24, 5 by M36, 10 by M48)
Scientific publications	9 scientific publications (3 by M24, 6 by M6, 9 by M48)

Table 11 – Communication and Dissemination KPIs

Annex 10 – Communication and dissemination reporting table

PARTNERS	TYPE	DATE	D&C ACTIVITY	VENUE	STATUS	GEOGRAPHICAL LEVEL	CONTEXT OF DISSEMINATION/ COMMUNICATION
PARTNER'S NAME	Activity type (Dissemination or Communication)	Date of the activity (DD/MM/YY)	Describe the type, the objectives and possible related output of the activity Please, enter the place and the date of the event	The venue of the activity (Place or ONLINE)	The status of the activity (select by menu)	GEOGRAPHICAL LEVEL (select by menu)	How the project has been disseminated? (select by menu)

1. Communication and dissemination reporting table

Figure 6 – Communication and dissemination reporting table (1)

TARGET GROUP Who was the project disseminated to? Numbers of participants per each category Involved											EVIDENCES	
Students*	Families	Education Scientific Community	Teachers	Schools	Policy Makers & Authorities	European Policy Makers	NGOs & Advocacy Organizations	Citizen, Media Outlet, General Public	Hits/ Views/ Visits on websites	Other (specify)	TOTAL (automatically Calculated)	Link the evidence of the activity (photos, videos, Clipping...) and attendance (signed lists, online report...) Or the link to the webpage (for online dissemination)

Figure 7 – Communication and dissemination reporting table (2)

The dissemination and communication table is composed by the following fields:

- Activity type → DISSEMINATION or COMMUNICATION
- Date of the activity

- Description of the activity → it must be accurate and understandable.
- Venue of the activity → write the name of the city where the activity took place or “ONLINE” for all digital/virtual activities (emails, online meetings, web articles, etc.)
- Status → To be chosen between DELIVERED (if the activity is closed) or ONGOING (if it still accessible after the publication/it is currently in progress)
- Geographical impact level → local, regional, national, European, international
- Context of dissemination → Conference, Education and training event, Information meeting, Clustering activity, Collaboration with EU-funded projects, Scientific collaboration, Scientific cooperation, Event, Exhibition, Fair, Interview, Media Article, Mailing list/Newsletter, Press release, Print Materials, Social Media, Promotional Video, TV/ radio campaign, Other.
- Target groups → for each group specify the number of attendees/addressees.
- Evidences → link to signatures /photo/ videos or to webpages/social media
- Notes → enter further details not mentioned before.

2. Publication reporting table

PARTNER	TYPE	PEER – REVIEW	PID		LINK	PUBLICATION			
Partner's name	Type of publication (select by menu)	Peer – review (YES/NO)	Type of PID (repository) (select by menu)	PID of deposited publication (insert PID of publication)	Link to publication (if no PID of publication)	Title of the publication (for book chapters: title of the chapter NOT of the book)	PID of publisher version of record	ISSN/eISSN (if book insert ISBN)	Authors

Figure 8 – Publication reporting table (1)

JOURNAL			DATE OF PUBLICATION	BOOK CHAPTER		OPEN ACCESS		
Title of the journal or equivalent	Number of the journal	Publisher of the journal	Month/Year of publication [MM/YYYY]	PID of book (if book chapter)	Book title (if book chapter)	Publication available in Open Access through the repository at the time of publication (YES/NO)	Charging of OA publishing fees to the project (YES/NO) If YES insert the amount!	License type (select menu)

Figure 9– Publication reporting table (2)

The **scientific publications table** is composed by the following fields:

- Type of publication → Article in journal, Publication in conference proceeding/Workshop, Book/Monograph, Chapter in book, Thesis/Dissertation, Other
- Peer-reviewd → Choose YES or NO
- Type of the PID [repository] → DO, Handle, ARK, URI, pURL, Other
- PID of deposited publications → Link to publication (if no PID of publication)
- Title of the publication (for book chapters: title of the chapter NOT of the book)
- PID of publisher version of record
- ISSN/eSSN (if book insert ISBN)
- Authors
- Title of the journal or equivalent
- Number of the journal
- Publisher of the journal

- Month/Year of publication
- PID of book (if book chapter)
- Book title (if book chapter)
- Publication available in Open Access through the repository at the time of publication (YES/NO)
- Charging of OA publishing fees to the project (YES/NO - If YES insert the amount)
- License type → CC BY NC or equivalent, CC BY NC or equivalent, CC BY NC ND or equivalent, Other licenses.

Annex 11 - Exploitation canvas explanatory overview

SUB-SECTION	SUMMARY AND HOW THE INFORMATION WILL BE USED
Value Proposition	This summarises the value that each product/service can bring to the customers and the marketplace. The information will be used to inform the Value Analysis exercise and marketing activities.
Customer Segments, Dissemination Channels and Relationships	This summarises who the partners feel will be interested in buying the product and / or service as developed, and the routes to be taken to reach these customers. It also provides an overview of the current relationships that can be used to accelerate the exploitation process, and new ones that need to be established. Licensing agreements, spin-off companies or other strategies would need to be discuss for scientific outputs. Discussion on plans for open access publication or sharing data to maximize the impact and usability of the research outcomes would take place. The information will be used to inform the “market entry plans” and marketing activities.
End-User Engagement	This summarises partner feedback as to whom it is best to approach for end-user validation, providing a qualified overview of opportunities and routes into established and new marketplaces. Partners assessed each customer segment and judged the level of value a customer would place on the result; how easy it would be to contact a customer (i.e. whether there is an existing relationship; whether the related sector is experiencing growth) and the likelihood of a customer agreeing to take part in the end-user validation process.
Key partners	This summarises the key stakeholders required per each partner to ensure the exploitation of the results in the market.
Cost Structure	This summarises the general approaches in order to analyse which are the most important costs inherent in the business model that must be defined.

	It has to be identified whether the business model is more cost-driven or value-driven.
Key Activities	This summarises the actions needed to accelerate the exploitation process and/or the technology upscaling if it is required.
Key Resources	This analysis will identify the specific resources (technological, manufacturing, etc.) required by the partner to exploit the results.

Table 12 - Business Model Explanatory overview

Annex 12 - Recommendations made by the IPR Helpdesk regarding results that are not protected

Best practice when deciding not to protect results:

If a partner does not intend to protect a result, according to IPR Helpdesk it is a best practice to consider offering to transfer it to other consortium partners or third parties, better positioned for the exploitation of the results and willing to seek their protection. If such transfer is not done, participants that have received European Union funding but do not intend to protect their results which are capable of industrial or commercial application for reasons other than legal impossibility, must be careful not to perform any dissemination activities without first informing the European Commission. This notification is mandatory up to four years after the end of the project. The European Commission may decide, with the consent of the participant to whom the result belongs to, to assume ownership and take the necessary measures to protect it.

Best practice when deciding to stop protection of results:

If a result is protected and a partner decides later to stop protection, this partner must notify the European Commission at least 60 days before the protection lapses or its extension is no longer possible up to four years after the project, except if:

- the protection is stopped because of a lack of potential for commercial or industrial exploitation or;
- the extension to further territories would not be justified.

The Commission must inform the participant on its decision also within 45 days of receiving the notification.